

ROLE OF PRATIMARSHYA NASAYA IN GADGAD VAAK IN CHILDREN: A CASE STUDYMane A.^{*1}, Kale S.², Ghorude N.³, Hubale S.⁴, Waykule V.⁵¹PG Scholar, Department of *Kaumarbhritya*, Yashwantrao Chavan Ayurvedic Medical College & Hospital, Chh. Sambhajnagar, Maharashtra.²Associate Professor, Department of *Kaumarbhritya*, Yashwantrao Chavan Ayurvedic Medical College & Hospital, Chh. Sambhajnagar, Maharashtra.³PG Scholar, Department of *Kaumarbhritya*, Yashwantrao Chavan Ayurvedic Medical College & Hospital, Chh. Sambhajnagar, Maharashtra.⁴PG Scholar, Department of *Kaumarbhritya*, Yashwantrao Chavan Ayurvedic Medical College & Hospital, Chh. Sambhajnagar, Maharashtra.⁵PG Scholar, Department of *Kaumarbhritya*, Yashwantrao Chavan Ayurvedic Medical College & Hospital, Chh. Sambhajnagar, Maharashtra.***Corresponding Author: Mane A.**PG Scholar, Department of *Kaumarbhritya*, Yashwantrao Chavan Ayurvedic Medical College & Hospital, Chh. Sambhajnagar, Maharashtra.DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18085238>**How to cite this Article:** Mane A.*1, Kale S.2, Ghorude N.3, Hubale S.4, Waykule V.5 (2026). Role Of Pratimarshya Nasaya In Gadgad Vaak In Children: A Case Study. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 12(1), 353–355.

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ABSTRACT

The diseases related to head and neck have *nasa* (nose) as important route for administration of medicine. Direct and quick transfer of medicine from thin mucosa of nasal cavity to systemic blood circulation has a greater impact in giving relief with early benefits. Language development occurs rapidly between 2 to 5 years of age. At this age repetition of words, speech learning, unclear speech takes place. When such conditions continues then they suffer from disability of speech. One of which is called *Gadgad vaak* (Stammering), a communication disorder. A 4 yr old male child having complaints of repetition of words while speaking, unclear speech (*aspastha vaak*), breaking of words while speaking (*sputa vaak*) was treated with *vyatishmati tail pratimarsha Nasaya* and results were noted by evaluating the symptomatic complaints. Detailed discussion of results and findings is done in this case report.

KEYWORDS: *Gadgad vaak*, *Jyotishmati tail*, *Nasaya karma*, Speech disorder.**INTRODUCTION**

In *Ayurveda* speech related problems mentioned are *Gadgad*, *minmin*, *mooka*, *swara bheda*, *vaak graha*. These lie under voice, articulatory and fluency disorder. *Gadgad* is symptom due to *avarana of samana vata* by *prana vata* in *avarana prakaran* by *acharaya charak*.^[1]

Gadgad is due to intake of *vata* aggravating *ahara vihar* by *garbhini* is said by *vrudha vagabhata*.^[2]

Vata gets *avarana* of *kapha* in *shabdavaha dhamani* producing *gadgad*, *mooka*, *minmintava* manifesting as speech disorder mentioned by *acharaya sushruta*.^[3]

These are the references in *ayurveda* regarding speech problems as it doesn't have any special category.

CASE DISCUSSION

A 4 years old male child presented with repetition of words while speaking, unclear speech and breaking of words while speaking.

Past history- No H/O of any major illness, or any drug allergy.

Antenatal history- No H/O any major illness during antenatal period.

Birth history- Full term normal delivered, no H/O any insult during labour.

Developmental milestones-

Gross motor, Fine motor, Social developmental milestones all are achieved as per age.

Monosyllables and bisyllables developed at the age of 12 months and 17 months of age respectively.

Immunization history- vaccinated as per schedule.

On examination- Repetition of words, unclear speech, breaking of words while speaking seen.

Strength of words decreased.

Accessory behaviors like eye movements vertically or laterally, loss of eye contacts while speaking, closing of eyes, facial grimacing etc. are seen.

No any systemic, local, muscular/anatomical abnormality found.

Analysis of speech done by frequency, nature of repetition and prolongation of words.

Diet history- Vegetarian and non vegetarian diet.

Past treatment history- No specific medication or therapy done for speech disorder.

Type of study- A case study.

Centre of study- *Kaumarbhritya* department OPD, YCAMC Hospital, Chh. Sambhajinagar.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Jyotishmati tail for *pratimarsha Nasaya*.

METHOD

Nasaya karma

Pratimarsha Nasaya of *Jyotishmati tail* daily twice for 60 days.

Patient follow up after every 15 days.

Assesment criteria for evaluation of patient:

Andrew's & Harries 1964.

Grade 0- Stutter not heard at interview

Grade 1- Mild stutter

Communication unimpaired

0-5% words stuttered

Grade 2 Moderate Stutter

Communication slightly impaired

6-20% words stuttered

Grade 3 Severe stutter

Communication definitely impaired over 20% words stuttered

Their codings for symptoms were:

A: Simple repetitions

B: Prolongations and hard blockings

C: Associated facial and body movements.

Grade 0- Up to 20sec.

Grade 1- Up to 30sec.

Grade 2- Up to 40sec.

Analysis of speech done by using reading alphabet charts, recitation of days, and 0-45 counting for 2 min.

DISCUSSION

The *lakshanas* seen were *Gharghara shabdha*, *svalpa asambaddha vaak*, *sphuta vaak*, *gardhabavat swara*, *aspashta vachana*, *avyakta vaak*, *lupta pada vyanjanadi*. Under *vata vyadhi chikitsa*, *avarana* of *vata acharaya charaka* and *sushruta* have mentioned the treatment of *gadgad vaak*.

Mode of action of *Jyotishmati tail* through *Pratimarsha Nasaya*

Latin Name: *Celastrus paniculatus*

Family : *Celastraceae*

Gana: Charak:- *Shirovirechan*

Sushrut:- *Adhobhaghar, Shirovirechan*.

<i>Rasa</i>	<i>Katu, Tikta</i>
<i>Guna</i>	<i>Tikshana, Snigdha</i>
<i>Virya</i>	<i>Ushna</i>
<i>Vipak</i>	<i>Katu</i>
<i>Prabhav</i>	<i>Medhya</i>

Nasya vidhi: *Bruhan nasya -Pratimarsha Nasya*^[4]

Nasya dosage: 2 bindu, one in each nostril.

Nasya kaal: *Prataha Kaal*.

Mode of action: *Prabhav Medhya*; *Virya ushna*; *katu vipak* works on *kapha dosh avrodha* in CNS hence promoting effective activity of speech delivery.

OBSERVATION OF SYMPTOMS

Sr. No.	Symptoms	Gradation		
		Before treatment	Mid treatment	After treatment
1.	Stuttering of words	3	2	1
2.	Hard blocks	2	2	1
3.	Communication	2	1	0
4.	Facial expression	2	2	1
5.	Prolongation of word	2	2	1
6.	Repetition of word	2	1	0

Probable mode of action of *Nasaya karma*

Avaran prakaran mentioned by *acharaya charak* states that *gadgad* is produced by *prana vaat* by making *avran* on *saman vaat*.^[5] They have mentioned *urdhva bhaag chikitsa* as line of treatment.^[6]

Acharya vagbhata states *tailam nasaye vatkapaharam* and says that *Nasaya* is indicated in *swarkshaya*.^[7]

Nasaya karma plays its role in three modes-

1. *Sirovirechan*

2. *Shaman*

3. *Tarpan karma* of *panchagnanendriya adhistana*.^[8]

CONCLUSION

The above case study shows that *Jyotishmati tail* when given as *Pratimarsha Nasaya* has a great impact in treatment of *aspashta vaak*, broken speech, *avyakta vaak*, facial expressions, repetitions of words.

The impact was seen even during follow-ups. The study was completed on patient with full duration of course and with zero adverse reaction. So, suggestive for treatment of *gadgad vaak* in children.

It was also noted that this management of *gadgad vaak* has a powerful impact on boosting self confidence and increasing patient's social involvement.

Adverse drug reaction: No any adverse drugs reaction found.

Conflict of Interest: None.

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Consent: A consent was taken from the patient before starting the treatment protocol as well as prior to publication of the case details and data.

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